

ANIQMAS INTEGRALLARNI HISOBLASH USULLARI

Meyliyev Sobir¹

¹TDPU dotsent vazifasini bajaruvchi o'qituvchisi

Mannopova Kumush²

²TDPU talabasi

Ikromboyeva Munisa³

³TDPU talabasi

Jo'rayeva Laylo⁴

⁴TDPU talabasi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7466429>

Annotasiya: Maqola olimpiada tanlovlaridagi aniqmas integrallarni hisoblashning umumiy va xususiy hollariga qaratilgan. Maqolada toq funksiyalar orqali hisoblash, integralni integrallar yig'indisiga ajratish bilan, integralni yangi o'zgaruvchi kiritish usullari bilan hisoblash ko'rsatilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: Aniq integral, Nyuton-Leybnis formulasi, toq funksiya, differensial, topmoq, chegaralangan, ko'phad, ayniyat, umumiy ko'paytuvchi, argument, yechim, bajarmoq, almashtirmoq.

Annotation: The article illustrates theorems concerning the methods of solving integral coefficient of polynomials in specific and common ways finding the solutions by odd functions, separating the sum of integrals and methods and adding changeable integers are shown in the following article.

Keywords: Definite integral, Newton-Leibniz formula, odd function, differential, to find, to be bounded, polynomial, identity, common factor, argument, solution, to carry out, to rearrange.

Аннотация: Статья основана общих и часты случание интеграла, выбора олимпиады точного и интегрального вычислений. В публикации показаны способы вычислений интеграл нечетных функций методом в ведение новой переменной.

Ключевые слова: Определенный интеграл, нечетная функция, дифференциал, найти, быть ограниченным, многочлен, тождество, общий множитель, аргумент, решение, выполнять, преобразовать.

Aniqmas integrallarni hisoblashning o'zgaruvchilarni almashtirish usuli jadvalda ko'rsatilmagan integrallarni jadvaldagi biror ko'rinishga keltirib hisoblash maqsadida qo'llaniladi. Bu usulning asosida murakkab funksiyani differensiallash qoidasi yotadi.

Faraz qilaylik $\int f(t)dt = F(t) + C$ bo'lsin. Bizdan $\int f(\varphi(x))dx$ integralni hisoblash talab etilgan bo'lsin. U holda $t = \varphi(x)$ almashtirish bajaramiz. Bundan

$$F(\varphi(x))' = F'(t) \cdot \varphi'(x) = f(t)\varphi'(x) = f(\varphi(x))\varphi'(x)$$

Demak: $\int f(\varphi(x))\varphi'(x)dx = F(\varphi(x)) + C$.

1) $\int \sin(2x+1) dx$ ni hisoblang.

Yechish: $t = 2x+1$ deb belgilasak $dt = (2x+1)' dx = 2dx \Rightarrow dx = \frac{1}{2} dt$

Demak, $\int \sin(2x+1) dx = \int (\sin t) \frac{1}{2} dt = \frac{1}{2} \int \sin t dt = -\frac{1}{2} \cos t + c = -\frac{1}{2} \cos(2x+1) + c$

2) $\int e^{\sin x} \cos x dx$ ni hisoblang.

Yechish: $\sin x = t$, $dt = (\sin x)' dx = \cos x dx$

demak, $\int e^{\sin x} \cos x dx = \int e^t dt = e^t + c = e^{\sin x} + c$

3) $\int \frac{\sin x dx}{\cos^4 x}$, $(x \neq \frac{\pi}{2} + k\pi, k \in Z)$ integralni hisoblang.

Yechish: $\cos x = t$ almashtirish bajaramiz. U holda $dt = d(\cos x) = -\sin x dx$. Demak, $\sin x dx = -dt$. Bundan:

$$\int \frac{\sin x dx}{\cos^4 x} = -\int \frac{dt}{t^4} = -\int t^{-4} dt = -\frac{t^{-3}}{-3} + C = \frac{1}{3t^3} + C = \frac{1}{3\cos^3 x} + C.$$

4) $\int \frac{6x^3 dx}{3x^4 + 7}$ integralni hisoblang.

Yechish: $t = 3x^4 + 7$ almashtirish bajaramiz. U holda $dt = 12x^3 dx \Rightarrow 6x^3 dx = \frac{1}{2} dt$.

$$\int \frac{6x^3 dx}{3x^4 + 7} = \int \frac{dt}{2t} = \frac{1}{2} \int \frac{dt}{t} = \frac{1}{2} \ln|t| + C = \frac{1}{2} \ln|3x^4 + 7| + C.$$

Aniqmas integralda bo'laklab integrallash usuli quyidagi formulaga asoslangan. Ma'lumki, $u(x)$ va $v(x)$ differensiallanuvchi funksiyalar bo'lsa

$$d(uv) = u dv + v du$$

formula o'rinli bo'ladi. Bundan:

$$u dv = d(uv) - v du$$

Tenglikning ikkala qismini integrallasak

$$\int u dv = uv - \int v du$$

formulani hosil qilamiz. Bu formula aniqmas integralda bo'laklab integrallash formulasi deyiladi.

1) $\int x e^x dx$ ni hisoblang.

Yechish: $u = x$, $du = dx$

$dv = e^x dx$ desak, $v = e^x$ bo'ladi.

$$\text{Demak, } \int u dv = \int u e^x dx = x \cdot e^x - \int e^x dx = x e^x - e^x + c$$

2) $\int x \sin x dx$ ni hisoblang.

Yechish: $u = x, dv = \sin x dx$ desak, $du = dx, v = \int \sin x dx = -\cos x$

$$\text{Demak, } \int u dv = \int x \sin x dx = -x \cos x + \int \cos x dx = -x \cos x + \sin x + c.$$

3) $\int x \ln x dx$ ni hisoblang.

Yechish. $u = \ln x, dv = x dx$ desak, $du = (\ln x)' dx = \frac{1}{x} dx,$

$$v = \frac{x^2}{2} \text{ bo'ladi. Demak, } \int x \ln x dx = \frac{x^2}{2} \ln x - \frac{1}{2} \int x^2 \cdot \frac{1}{x} dx = \frac{x^2}{2} \ln x - \frac{1}{2} \int x dx =$$

$$= \frac{x^2}{2} \ln x - \frac{x^2}{4} + c.$$

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Fayziboyev va boshqalar. Oliy matematikadan misollar. Toshkent. «O'zbekiston». 1999.
2. A.Rasulov. Ehtimolliklar nazariyasi va matematik statistika. Toshkent. "Turon-Bo'ston". 2012 y.
3. Susanna S. Epp. Discrete mathematics with applications, Fourth Edition. Cengage Learning. Boston, USA-2011. (ISBN 978-0-495-39132-6)
4. Jane S Paterson Heriot-Watt (University Dorothy) A Watson Balerno (High School) SQA Advanced Higher Mathematics. Unit 1. This edition published in 2009 by Heriot-Watt University SCHOLAR. Copyright © 2009 Heriot-Watt University. (ISBN 978-1-906686-03-1)
5. Valentin Deaconu, Don Pfaff. A bridge course to higher mathematics. Current address : Department of Mathematics, University of Nevada, Reno NV 89557-0084, USA.
E-mail address : vdeaconu@unr.edu
6. Hamedova N.A. va bosh. "Matematika". OO'Yu uchun darslik, T.: Turon iqbol, 2007y.
1. www.tdpu.uz
2. www.pedagog.uz
3. www.edu.uz
4. www.nadlib.uz (A.Navoiy nomidagi O'z.MK)

5. <http://ziyonet.uz> — "Ziyonet" axborot-ta'lim resurslari portali

